

The Balts and Kievan Rus'. New Baltic cemetery in Ukraine

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ZBSA Scientific Colloquium, 22. November 2018, organizer: Dr. Roman Shiroukhov

1 Participants of the "The Balts and Kievan Rus'" colloquium at Schloss Gottorf, Balkonzimmer (photo: R. Shiroukhov).

2 Flat ladder brooch of the Baltic style from Ostriv-1 grave 2 *in situ* (photo: V. Baranov).

Two years ago, Ukrainian scientists found an early medieval cemetery which will soon become one of the most important archaeological finds in post-soviet Ukrainian history: the early medieval Ostriv-1 necropolis of the Baltic migrants.

After a year of intensive correspondence and exchange of impressions with one of the researchers, Vyacheslav Baranov, I had the opportunity to visit this site in September 2018. During this trip, the first steps for a potential international cooperation were taken. After this visit, it was decided to arrange the next scientific meeting in Schleswig.

On November 22, the ZBSA Colloquium "The Balts and Kievan Rus'. New Baltic cemetery in Ukraine" was held at Schloss Gottorf with the participation of archaeologists Dr. Vsevolod Ivakin and Vyacheslav Baranov MA and anthropologist Dr. Oleksandra Kozak from the Institute of Archaeology of the National Academy of Science of Ukraine (Kiev). The papers of the colloquium "New Baltic Necropolis of the 11–12th Centuries in the Middle Dnieper Region" (V. Ivakin, V. Baranov), "Anthropology of Baltic Necropolis of the 11–12th Century Ostriv-1. First Results and Perspectives (O. Kozak)", "The Balts and Ostriv-1 Cemetery", "Origins of Grave Goods and Burial Rite" (R. Shiroukhov) attracted a lot of interest and discussion among ZBSA members. Indeed, a Late Viking Age/early medieval cemetery of presumably Baltic migrants, connected with Scandinavian Balts and Kievan Rus' artefacts and ideas, is a good starting point for future interdisciplinary collaboration. Moreover, today on the Sambian

Peninsula (Kaliningrad region, Russia), we have a lot of archaeological evidence of intensive trade contacts between the territories of the Prussians and Kievan Rus'.

Here are some more details about the Ostriv-1 cemetery: the necropolis is located on the low terrace of the River Ros near the village of Ostriv, approximately 100 km south of Kiev. During 2017–2018, excavations by V. Ivakin and V. Baranov over an area of 1,000 m² uncovered 53 inhumation graves with a north orientation (which is untypical for Kievan Rus'). Most of the grave goods belong to the 11–12th centuries and are characteristic first of all of several Baltic tribes: Prussians, Curonians, Scalvians and Semigallians. These can be east Baltic region migrants connected with the Jaroslaw the Wise migration and defence politics of the first half of the 11th century, mentioned in written sources. According to O. Kozak's anthropological analysis, the first results of the morphological study of the skeletal remains demonstrated that the paleopopulation of Ostriv-1 was rather young (the average age at death being 35 years) with a very low proportion of children. The population has a low adaptation level, which could be characteristic of incomers in the first waves of migrations. The same can be said about several types of brooches of the Western Balt types, which usually have signs of repair at the sites of their origin, but not here at Ostrov-1. It can also point to the first generation of Baltic migrants.

ZBSA and Kiev archaeologists are planning further field, laboratory and analytical research into the Ostriv-1 cemetery as part of a new international project.

